

HISTOGENESIS OF THE THYROID AND PARATHYROID GLANDS IN BUFFALO

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ABSTRACT

A total of 38 buffalo fetuses were used in the present study and their CRL ranged from 0.9 cm to 80.0 cm CRL. In buffalo five pharyngeal pouches were noted at 0.9 cm CRL (26 days). The third pharyngeal pouch showed a common primordium for parathyroid III and thymus at 1.2 cm CRL (28 days). At 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) parathyroid and thymic primordia lost their connection with the pharynx. Thyroid primordium noted as a median diverticulum of the floor of the pharynx at 1.2 cm CRL (28 days). At 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) thyroid primordium showed two distinct lobes and they were connected by unpaired isthmus. At 19.5 cm CRL (115 days) formation of thyroid follicles as well as follicular epithelium was began and thyroid was highly vascular at this stage. At 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) thyroid follicles and follicular epithelium were distinct. At this stage colloid substance was characteristically seen in thyroid glands of buffalo. Many reticular fibers were also reported between the follicles at this stage.

Keywords: histogenesis, thyroid gland, parathyroid glands, buffalo

INTRODUCTION

The thyroid and parathyroid glands are derivatives of the embryonic pharyngeal region (Boyd, 1954). The embryonic development of thyroid and parathyroid glands have been studied in hamster (Ackerman and Knouff, 1964) and dog (Hendrickx, 1964).

But no information is available on development of thyroid and parathyroid glands in buffalo. Therefore, a comprehensive study on histogenesis of thyroid and parathyroid glands has been undertaken in buffalo. This will be contributory to the existing anatomical knowledge and it will provide a basis for future investigations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 38 buffalo foetuses were used for the present study and their CRL (crown rump length) varied from 9.0 cm to 80.0 cm (26 days to 254 days). Buffalo foetuses of different gestational age were collected from non descript buffaloes, sacrificed in and around Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh. The CRL was measured as a curved line along the vertebral column between the most anterior part of frontal bone to the ischiatic tuberosity (Edward, 1965). The approximate age of the foetus was determined on the basis of their CRL by using

Soliman's formulae (1975). After measuring the CRL, the small embryos of less than 6.0 cm CRL were fixed as a whole, while from large embryos thyroid and parathyroid glands were dissected out and fixed in 10 percent neutral buffered formalin.

The fixed tissues were processed for paraffin blocks by acetone benzene schedule. The paraffin sections of 5-6 µm were subjected to Mayer's haematoxylin and eosin for normal histomorphology, Gridley's method for reticular fibres and Verhoeff's method for elastic fibres (Luna, 1968).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study 0.9 cm CRL (26 days) embryo was the youngest in which five pairs of pharyngeal pouches were noted between the brachial arches on the lateral wall of the pharyngeal entoderm. The last one of these (fifth) was small and appeared to be absorbed into the fourth pharyngeal pouch resulting in the formation of caudal pharyngeal pouch complex. The pharyngeal pouches in buffalo were numbered I to IV in cephalocaudal sequence (Figure 1). Similarly, Kingsbury (1935), Noden and De Lahunta (1985) in cattle and Prasad and Singh (1990) in goat stated that the fifth pharyngeal pouch never attained the morphological value of a definite pouch. The first and second pouches were small and shallower, whereas the third pouch was the largest of all.

At 1.2 cm CRL (28 days) stage the entoderm of the third pharyngeal pouch showed extensive proliferation of epithelial cells that led to formation of a common primordium for both parathyroid and thymus. The dorsal part of this primordium was differentiated into a solid bar of tissue that transformed into external parathyroid

glands. This parathyroid tissue was referred to as parathyroid III, which denoted its origin (Latshaw, 1987). The ventral part of the primordium was initially tubular and transformed into a definitive thymus in the subsequent stage of development. Similarly, Latshaw (1987) in domestic animals reported dorsal solid and ventral tubular portions in the primordium of the third pharyngeal pouch. The entodermal cells of the dorsal diverticulum of the fourth pharyngeal pouch developed in a manner similar to their counter-parts of the third pouch that led to formation of parathyroid IV (Figure 2). Latshaw (1987) termed these parathyroids as caudal or internal parathyroids in ruminants. The ultimobranchial bodies were developed from the caudal pharyngeal pouch at 2.5 cm CRL (Figure 2).

At 2.5 cm CRL stage (40 days) the parathyroid and thymic primordia lost their connection with the pharynx. According to Hendrickx (1964), the connection between the pharynx and primordium of the third pharyngeal pouch was lost between 26 days to 28 days of gestation in dog. Later the two primordia were separated from each other and migrated to their definitive locations.

The epithelial cells of the parathyroid primordium were recognizably different in structure from those of thymic primordium. The parathyroid primordium appeared more lightly stained than the thymic primordium and was devoid of lymphocytes. The parathyroid III primordium was placed dorsal to the thymic primordium (Figure 3). Whereas parathyroid IV placed dorsal to the thyroid primordium and 3rd aortic arch and maintained its integrity as caudal or internal parathyroids (Figure 4). These findings were in accordance with the observations of Ackerman and Knouff (1964) in the embryonic hamster. Further, they mentioned

that parathyroid gland showed strong PAS reaction in contrast with the thymus.

Thyroid gland:

In the present study, primordium of thyroid gland first noted as a median diverticulum of the floor of the pharynx at 1.2 cm CRL (28 days). Whereas, Boyd (1950) noted thyroid primordium in 17-18 somite embryos of human. Histogenesis of the thyroid gland began at about 2.5 cm CRL (40 days). At this stage, the thyroid primordium showed two distinct lobes on either side of the developing trachea and they were connected by unpaired isthmus ventrally (Figures 3 and 4). The cords of entodermal cells from the thyroid diverticulum eventually branched into isolated growths and they transformed into thyroid follicles. At this stage cells were darkly stained and showed distinct nucleus. At 19.5 cm CRL (115 days) the thyroid primordium showed formation of follicles and follicular epithelium, at this stage thyroid was highly vascular (Figure 5). This may facilitate entrance of

thyroid hormones into the bloodstream as opined by Latshaw (1987). In the present study, at 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) characteristic thyroid follicles were noted in the thyroid of buffalo and they were lined by cuboidal epithelium. At this stage, a distinct colloid substance was also observed in the follicles (Figure 6). These findings suggested that the thyroid of buffalo was functional from early foetal life for normal growth and development as opined by Latshaw (1987) in ruminants. Further, he stated that thyroxine cannot pass through the placenta and the thyroid is a capable of forming thyroxine by about 35 days or earlier and functioning during the second trimester in ruminants. Formation of a capsule around the gland was noticed from the surrounding mesenchyme at 19.5 cm CRL (115 days). This capsule was distinct at 31.0 cm CRL (143 days) and in later stages of development. In the present study reticular fibres were few and were in formative stage at 115 days of gestation. However, they were characteristically seen at 143 days (Figure 7) and in subsequent stages of development

Figure 1. Photomicrograph of buffalo embryo of 0.9 cm CRL (26 days) showing branchial arch I (B1), branchial arch II (B2), branchial arch III (B3), branchial arch IV (B4), Pharyngeal pouch I (P1), Pharyngeal pouch II (P1I), Pharyngeal pouch III (PIII), and Pharyngeal pouch IV (P4), Aortic arch III (A3), and Aortic arch IV (A4). H&E x100.

Figure 2. Photomicrograph of buffalo embryo of 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) showing developing oesophagus (O), Trachea (Tr), Parathyroid primordium (P3), Thymic primordium III (T3), Aortic arch III (A3), Parathyroid IV (P4), Ultimobranchial bodies (U) and Thyroid primordium (Th). H&E x100.

Figure 3. Photomicrograph of buffalo embryo of 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) at higher magnification showing developing oesophagus (O), Trachea (Tr), Parathyroid primordium (P3), Thymic primordium III (T3), Aortic arch III (A3), Erythroblasts (E) and Thyroid primordium (Th). H&E x200.

Figure 4. Photograph of 31 cm CRL (143 days) buffalo foetus showing Thyroid (T) Parathyroid glands (P) and Isthmus (I).

Figure 5. Photomicrograph of buffalo foetus of 19.5 CRL (115 days) showing developing thyroid follicles and follicular epithelium (F) and blood vessels (B) around the follicles. H&E x400.

Figure 6. Photomicrograph of Buffalo foetus of 31 cm CRL (143 days) showing thyroid follicles and follicular epithelium (F) and colloid substance (C) and distinct parafollicular cells (P). H&E x400.

Figure 7. Photomicrograph of buffalo foetus of 31 cm CRL (143 days) showing well developed reticular fibres (R) between the thyroid follicles (F). Gridley's x 400.

of thyroid in buffalo. Few elastic fibers were noted in the developing capsule and blood vessels of the capsule at 115 days of gestation.

The ultimobranchial bodies were incorporated into the thyroid gland at 2.5 cm CRL (40 days) and these cells positioned between the developing thyroid follicles and these cells were termed as parafollicular cells by Latshaw (1987). These cells can be easily distinguished amidst the substance of the thyroid by their large size and pale staining properties.

REFERENCES

- Ackerman, G.A. and R.A. Knouff. 1964. Lymphocyte formation in the thymus of the embryonic chick. *Anat. Rec.*, **149**: 191-216.
- Boyd, J.D. 1950. Development of the thyroid and parathyroid glands and the thymus in human. *Lecture of Royal College of Surgeons*, **1**: 455-471.
- Edward, M.J. 1965. Observations on the anatomy of the reproductive organs of cow. *Newzealand Vety. Journal.*, **13**: 25.
- Latshaw, W.K. 1987. *Developmental Anatomy*. B.C. Decker Inc., Ontario, Canada. 104-108p.
- Luna, L.G. 1968. *Manual of Histological Staining Methods of the Armed Forces Institute of Pathology*, 3rd ed. McGraw Hill book co., New York, USA.
- Noden, D.M. and A. De Lahahunta. 1985. *The Embryology of Domestic Animals*, 2nd ed. Williams and Wilkins, Baltimore, Maryland. 277p.
- Prasad, R. and Y. Singh. 1990. Histogenesis and fate of the ultimobranchial bodies in goat fetuses. *Indian J. Ani. Sci.*, **63**: 390-395.
- Soliman, M.K. 1975. Studies on the physiological

chemistry of the allantoic and amniotic fluid of buffaloes at various periods of pregnancy. *Indian Vety. J.*, **52**: 106-111.

Hendrickx, A.G. 1964. The pharyngeal pouches of the dog. *Anat. Rec.*, **149**: 475-483.

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Figure 2. Photomicrograph showing lymphocytic, polymorphocytic, lymphoblastic, histocytic types which were inter mixed cell types. H&E $\times 70$.